

STRESS, STUDY HABITS AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF STUDENTS IN CAVITE STATE UNIVERSITY- CARMONA CAMPUS

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Stress, Study Habits and Academic Performance of Students in Cavite State University-Carmona Campus

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Abstract

This study was conducted to determine the level of stress, the quality of study habits, and the level of academic performance of CvSU Carmona Campus students during the pandemic, and the relationship between these factors. A modified questionnaire was utilized to gather data from one thousand six hundred eighty-six (1,686) students coming from the campus' different programs. Answers were tabulated and interpreted using mean and standard deviation, average score, chi-square, and ANOVA. Results of the study revealed that most students have a low level of stress in terms of relationship and body, mind, and feelings while a high level of stress in terms of school-related factors. This reveals students have high stress in matters related to school activities and that they are emotionally and physically drained by the demands of the school. Their study habits proved to be good, while their academic performance showed to be very good. Relatively, there is a significant relationship between the level of stress of the participants and their level of academic performance, and between their quality of study habits and level of academic performance. With this, it was suggested that the different departments of the campus, in collaboration with the Office of Student Affairs and Services, formulate wellness programs that would lessen the stress of the students in terms of school-related activities such as support groups from the different student organizations and stress management webinars.

Keywords: *stress, study habits, academic performance*

Introduction

The news about the novel Corona Virus (COVID 19) shocked the world during the first quarter of 2020. Several confirmed acquisitions of the virus and deaths with it came placing the entire Luzon into an enhanced community quarantine. This was further extended to avoid the spread of the virus. This lockdown has affected much of the education system.

Due to this, the governments around the world closed all the educational institutions to control the advancement of the disease. This created a direct effect on students, faculty members and educational institutions from all levels. The abrupt change of classroom setting, from doing the teaching method face to face which students are used to, to having the remote mode of teaching, created a big adjustment for them. This brought stress and mental health consequences not only to educators but also to students (Chandra, 2020). A large number of students are going through early life issues such as, but not limited to, anxiety, depression, infection fear, and ambiguity due to the lockdown related to it. School loads add up with not being allowed to get out of their houses because of quarantine rules. Moreover, most of the time, students are left doing their schoolwork alone and far from their physical friends. In the Philippines, several studies have already been done proving that stress affects the academic performance of students. Moreover, study habits are characterized as actions that include reading, taking notes, and doing group studies, which the students perform regularly and habitually to be able to accomplish the task of learning. In this manner, study habits can either be effective or not depending on their effect on the achievement of a student.

Cavite State University (CvSU) Carmona Campus is one of the satellite campuses of the premier university in Cavite. One of the goals of the campus is to develop highly competent human resources by ensuring an enriching environment to promote professional growth and career advancement for the faculty, staff, and students. With this, CvSU Carmona has always aimed to be at its best in producing globally competitive and morally upright individuals. In the occurrence of the pandemic, one of the concerns of the institution is to be able to assist students in all concerns as much as they can, one of which is considering their general welfare. The Office of the Students Affairs and Services Office gathered some concerns of the students and data were collected through student profile inventory of students. Results showed that, consecutively, from A.Y. 2018-2019 and A.Y. 2019-2020, 34.12% and 33.15% of the students reported mental health concerns. Self-reported concerns include depression, stress, family problems, alcohol abuse, anger, and time management issues. As presented, stress is one of the top three reasons for student concerns other than self-reported depression and family problems. The percentage may be a small percentage on the sight, but it is a big concern for institutions that aim to be able to produce the best students, even in the new normal.

This study then was proposed to determine the level of stress on online teaching or learning brought into the students of CvSU Carmona during this pandemic. This will also identify the possible changes in their study habits from the usual routine they used to have prior to the COVID-19 dilemma. Proponents would also like to verify if these have any effect in their academic performance. Whatever result this may lead would be a great support to formulate action plans such as strategies to cope with stress and strategies to improve their study habits and academic performance. Moreover, since this is a student-related concern, this study also targeted to assist the Office of the Student Affairs and Services with one of its activity objectives which was to provide support to the needs of the

stakeholders concerning mental health and be able to gather necessary information in developing appropriate programs that are relevant and responsive to the student's particular needs.

Research Objectives

Therefore, these facts led the researchers to study further the stress level and the study habits of the students of CvSU Carmona Campus during the A.Y. 2021-2022 and its effects on their academic performance. Generally, the program would like to:

1. Determine the level of stress of the students in Cavite State University – Carmona in terms of:
 - 1.1. school-related factors;
 - 1.2. relationship; and
 - 1.3. body, mind and feelings.
2. Determine the quality of study habits of the students in Cavite State University – Carmona in terms of:
 - 2.1. motivation;
 - 2.2. organizing and planning;
 - 2.3. working with others, utilizing resources and feedback; and
 - 2.4. note-taking and reading.
3. Determine the level of academic performance of the students in Cavite State University – Carmona;
4. Determine the significant relationship between the level of stress of the participants and the level of the academic performance in terms of:
 - 4.1. school-related factors and academic performance;
 - 4.2. relationship and academic performance; and
 - 4.3. body and mind feelings and academic performance.
5. Determine the significant relationship between the quality of study habits and the level of academic performance of the students in terms of:
 - 5.1. motivation and academic performance;
 - 5.2. organizing and planning and academic performance;
 - 5.3. working with others, utilizing resources and feedback and academic performance; and
 - 5.4. note-taking and reading and academic performance.
6. Formulate action plans, based on the results, to help students cope with stress and to improve quality of study habits in the context of new normal.

Literature Review

Stress

Stress is a feeling of emotional or physical tension. It is believed that the body reacts to the changes in the environment, one's thoughts and body with physical, mental, and emotional responses. It has also been defined as the physiological and psychological experience of significant life events, trauma, and chronic strain (Thoits, 2010). Stress can lead to different physical symptoms.

Supposedly, to be able to cope up with stress, one has to completely understand its theory. Stress has been viewed as a response, a stimulus, and a transaction. Stress, as stimulus theory, assumes that (1) any change in life is naturally stressful, (2) any life events have the same levels of adjustment or modification at all times in all ages, and (3) there is a common origin of adjustment which may result to illness. Stangor and Walinga (2014) initially regarded humans as passive recipients of stress and cannot determine the stressor's intensity, degree, or valence.

Stress of Students

According to some studies, there is already an alarming increase of stress among the young generations. With the life changes in people now because of the whole world's dilemma, stress is inevitable, especially with students. Other studies specified that students in secondary and tertiary education face a wide range of ongoing stressors or pressures, which is known as a normal day to day difficulties in their ongoing academic demands. Students commonly have reports that they experience ongoing stress relating to their studies, which is referred to as academic-related stress This includes pressure to achieve high marks and concerns and anxiety of receiving poor grades (Pascoe et al., 2020).

Several studies have already been done to measure the stress of students in the Philippines. According to Mazo (2015), stress can be found everywhere. It can be experienced at home, in the office, in school, and even in the classroom or with friends. This cannot be avoided because it is part of being human and is present in every corner. Same result was highlighted in another study of Austria-Cruz (2019) where it was postulated that the major contributors of college students' stress include the teachers, peers who commit cheating and completion of requirements. With that, students felt academically stressed and challenged, thus, they experience sleeping problems, low self-confidence, and irritability or agitations. Though based on it, students were able to cope up through spirituality, which is one of the best traits of Filipinos, it was still recommended that educational institutions need to comply with the mental health needs of students, thus, creating strategies to attain their best well-being.

Study Habits of Students

Study habits are the behaviors used by students when they are asked to prepare for a test or needs to learn some academic materials. It is believed that the vital reason for becoming an effective student is learning how to study smarter and not harder. As students advance in education, it is believed that one improves by having a good strategy in studying. Giving an hour or two the whole day and allotting it for studying is usually adequate to make it through secondary school with satisfactory grades. But when college comes, one has to find more smarter and keener approaches of facing the demands of the educational institutions (Polikoff et al., 2020). Study habits are believed to contribute significantly in the development of knowledge and perceptual capacities of a student. Majority of academically successful students are known to use and develop effective study habits.

Study Habits and Academic Achievement

Webster dictionary defined a habit as “an acquired mode of behavior that has become nearly or completely involuntary”. It is learned and is considered to be a norm in anyone’s life as time passes. There is even a myth that for a habit to form, one should be able to continuously do the action in a minimum of 21 days. This can be traced back from the book published by Dr. Maxwell Maltz in 1960 (healthline.com). Theories also propose that habit has two effects on behavior of individuals. First, a habit will elicit frequent performance, and second, it will supersede the motivational tendencies in doing so, unless there is strong self-control in that moment (Gardner & Rebar, 2019). This shows that even if they are not motivated at such a time, a habit will still be done and executed.

Consequently, Jato, Ogunniyi, & Olubiyo (2014) considered study habits as actions such as reading, taking notes and doing group studies which the students perform regularly and consistently to be able to accomplish the task of learning. Study habits can either be effective or not depending on its effect on the achievement of a student. In different studies, study habits have been connected with the Theory of Educational Productivity of Walberg in 1981 which was analytically tested as one of very theories of academic achievement. He identified nine important variables that can influence educational results. This includes student ability or prior achievement, motivation, age or developmental level, quantity of instruction or subject load, quality of instruction of teachers, the classroom climate or classroom management, home environment, peer group they join, and the exposure to mass media outside of the school (Rugutt & Chemosit, 2005). With these theories mentioned, it supposes that habits and academic performance are correlated and affects one another.

Academic Performance

Academic performance is often coined with the general point average (GPA) of students. Studies show that there should be motivation and learning strategy used to improve student learning outcomes (Gbollie & Keamu, 2017). Liem (2019) quoted that “scholars agree that students’ academic achievement is a ‘net result’ of their cognitive and non-cognitive attributes as well as the sociocultural context in which the learning process takes place.

Relationship of Stress and Academic Performance

Several studies show that there is significant relationship between stress and academic performance. In the study of G-Oboth and Odiemo (2018), the correlation between stress level and academic performance was significant among students who are 19 to 22 years and 23 to 26 years, both males and females. It reveals that stress affects the student’s academic performance. Elias, Ping, and Abdullah (2011) also studied the stress and academic performance of undergraduate students. The study findings presented that the undergraduate students experienced moderate levels of stress. Moreover, findings exhibited that the students of first-year level had low stress with academics as the most valuable reasons of stress. A significant but weak negative relationship between undergraduate students’ stress level and their academic achievement was also found in the study.

The Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) survey reports that anxiety about schoolwork, homework and tests have a negative effect on students’ academic performance in science, mathematics and reading. Pascoe, Hetrick, and Parker (2020) even stated that academic-related stresses are a major concern for secondary and tertiary students. The ongoing stress that students have demonstrated had negative impact on students’ learning capacity, academic performance, education and employment attainment, physical and mental health, sleep quality and quantity, and substance use outcomes. It is suggested then that trainings on students’ stress-management skills and abilities be given to students.

Relationship of Study Habits of Students and Academic Performance

Study habits were found to be the most important predictor of academic performance and play a special role in the academic achievement of students (Jafari et al., 2019). It is believed that when students have their study habits, this can lead to good performance. The study recommended to consider and assess the study habits of students at the time of entry into the university. In addition, trainings are recommended to be offered to students in order to help them learn or modify their study habits to increase their academic achievements. Likewise, in the study of Reyes and Astrologo (2011), it was revealed that for one to have a good academic performance, it requires good study habits. They recommended that all stakeholders in education which includes, the parents, teachers, and government should encourage students in their respective areas of responsibilities such as, but not limited to, providing study materials, having a good study area, rewarding and recognizing excellent performance and hard work. All these are suggested so to motivate students perform at their best in school.

Another study on college students under medical science revealed that in terms of eight areas of study habits, there were undesirable study habits which resulted in most students which are the areas of taking notes and well-being, while it is desirable in the area of time (Jafari et al., 2019). On the other hand, the study habits of the rest of the students in other areas was at moderate level. The same was introduced by Akpan and Salome (2015) as they concluded that there should be valuable time expended on studying and make it a habit. They also further recommended that good teaching methods and good peer groups must be encouraged to bring out good reading culture in the students.

In the Philippines, several studies were also taken into account to measure the relationship of the study habits of students and their academic performance. Carbonel (2013) determined the learning styles, study habits, and academic performance of college students in Kalinga-Apayao as to their Algebra subject. Results implied that the study habits of the students have great impact in their performance in the subject where they are performing averagely. It was also mentioned that students' attitudes also affect the performance.

Methodology

Respondents

The respondents of the study were the students of Cavite State University – Carmona specifically for the 1st Semester A.Y. 2021-2022. All programs offered in CvSU-Carmona were involved namely Bachelor of Science in Business Management major in Human Resource Management (BSBM HRM) and major in Marketing Management (BSBM MM), Bachelor of Science in Hospitality Management (BSHM), Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSE), Bachelor of Science in Information Technology (BSIT), Bachelor of Science in Computer Science (BSCS), Bachelor of Science in Industrial Technology (BSIT) and Bachelor of Science in Computer Engineering (BSCpE).

Moreover, the Z-score formula for the known population was used to get the number of participants from the total population, which was proportionately distributed from all the different programs on the campus. Tables 1 shows the distribution of the participants from each program.

Table 1. *Distribution of the participants*

<i>Program/ Majorship</i>	<i>Population (N=3,678)</i>	<i>Sample Size (n=1,686)</i>
BSBM Major in Marketing	675	317
BSBM Major in Human Resource Management	483	235
BS in Hospitality Management	503	224
Bachelor in Secondary Education	656	246
BS in Information Technology	691	284
BS in Computer Science	204	135
BS in Industrial Technology	252	120
BS in Computer Engineering	214	122
Total	3,678	1,686

Instrument

Adopted and modified research instruments were applied in the study. The instrument for the level of stress came from the standardized questionnaire of Barreca and Kepler in 2020 used in the study titled “Stress Among Youth: A Wakeup Call for Society” by Pandey (2014). Meanwhile, the level of quality of the student's study habits was adopted from the works of Bulusan et al. (2019) in their book *Facilitating Learner-Centered Teaching*.

The research instrument was divided into three parts. The first part included the demographic profile of the participants in terms of age, sex, program, year and section which were intended for the profiling of the participants. The second part was intended to determine the level of stress of the students in terms of school related factor; relationship factor; and body mind and feelings factor. The last part of the questionnaire was intended to determine the level of quality of the students' study habits in terms of motivation; organizing and planning; working with others, utilizing resources and feedback; and note taking and reading.

For the academic performance of the students, the researchers coordinated with the registrar's office to get the general pointed average grades of the participants of the study. The GPA to be considered was the obtained GPA for 1st semester 2021-2022 (September 2021 to January 2022).

Procedure

Requests of information on the number of students were initially provided by the Registrar's Office, after which, another approval was sent to the Campus Administrator to disseminate the questionnaire through google forms. The link of the questionnaire was given to the class presidents of each program for them to assist in the dissemination to their classmates. A separate request letter was given to the Registrar to get the general average grade of the students who answered the survey. Once the target number of participants was reached, the data gathered was tallied, encoded and analyzed and interpreted.

Frequency count and percentage were used to determine the profile of the students who participated in the study. Mean and standard deviation were used to determine the level of stress of the students. Descriptive interpretations for the level of stress of the participants is displayed in Tables 9 to 11. Meanwhile, frequency count was used to get the sum of the scores of the students to determine the quality of their study habits. Lastly, Chi-square was used to know the significant relationship between level of stress and students' academic performance, and the significant relationship between quality of study habits and student performance.

Ethical Considerations

Observing ethical standards in research was applied in this study. Taking into consideration the data privacy policy, only the researchers involved in the study had access on the results. The responses in the google form link were visible only to the project and study leaders of each program. Personal information of the participants was not disclosed and results were kept in an excel file with security password. After the completion of the study and after research publication, the said information gathered was deleted.

Results and Discussion

Results were tabulated and interpreted as required by the study.

Level of Stress of Students in Cavite State University (CvSU) – Carmona Campus

Table 2 shows the level of stress of the students, in terms of different facets, from the different programs of the Cavite State University (CvSU) Carmona Campus. It shows that most of the students have low level of stress in terms of their relationship with others and their body, mind and feelings. It presents that generally, the students are emotionally and physically drained with the demands of their school but are somehow emotionally and physically drained by their social relationships, which include their family and friends, and in terms of their body, mind and feelings.

Table 2. *Level of Stress of Students*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
School-related factors	2.61	0.49	High
Relationship	1.85	0.63	Low
Body, mind and feelings	2.20	0.72	Low
Grand Mean	2.242		

School-related factors. Table 2 reveals a mean score of 2.61 and a standard deviation of 0.49 for the level of stress of students in terms of school-related factors. It clearly shows that they have a high stress in matters related to school activities. They are emotionally and physically drained with the demands of their program, their professors, and the university which makes them doubtful if they may succeed in their studies. Most of the student-participants fear that they will fail their course or program, believe that even if they pass their exams, they are worried about getting a job, and that the amount of work assignments given to them by their teachers is too much. All these led to a high level of stress in this matter.

Even before the pandemic, Mazo (2015) revealed that the most common reason of stress of female students are requirements or projects which leads them to sleepless nights and having more irritable moods. On the other hand, for the males, these student experiences also give them sleepless nights which lead to low performance at school. In a different study among college students, Dy, Espiritu-Santo, Ferido, and Sanchez (2015) exposed the top five stressors of the students. These included academic difficulty of subject matter, responsibilities due to doing things or tasks on their own, time management and the workload because of their subjects and workload due to their organizations. This is true especially now that students are still in their remote learning mode. Even in Austria-Cruz's (2019) study on college students from public and private universities in Central Luzon, it was found out that the main causes of student stress include meeting the requirements given by the teachers.

Relationship. In terms of relationship with others, it reveals that CvSU students have a low level of stress in this aspect with a mean of 1.85 and a standard deviation of 0.63. Generally, it reveals that the students somehow have a good relationship with their family, friends, and classmates which does not make them feel troubled and disoriented. It is being justified with the responses of the students believing that they do not have problems in having friends, or experiencing conflict with their classmates during classes and having conflict with them. Likewise, they do not have trouble getting along with their family members. It clearly shows that they can still balance their relationships, even in this pandemic. This is in contrast with the result of the qualitative research of Hurst, Baranik and Daniel (2012), where it was revealed that relationship stressors were the most commonly reported stressors for college students which included stress relating to family, their romantic relationships and their relationships with their peers and teachers.

Body, Mind and Feelings. With a mean score of 2.20 and a standard deviation of 0.720, students have a low level of stress in this matter. Generally, the students are somehow in good physical, mental, and emotional condition which made them focused on their studies. Most of them only slightly agree that they do not feel like anyone cares for them since they enrolled in their course/ program. Also, they believe they do not want to do things that they used to like, and that they feel sad or depressed since they enrolled in their program. With the results and literature, it is seen that usual causes of stress for university students are these three factors— relationship with others, their current state of body mind and feelings and school-related ones. Thus, even not in the pandemic these factors do lead to stress and were even effectors these times of remote learning in remaining parts of the world, including the Philippines.

The significant difference between the stress level of the different programs in the campus were also tested. It can be seen that the level of stress in terms of school-related factors and body, mind and feelings of the students from all the programs of the campus, when compared to one another, are significantly different from one another (Table 3). But the level of stress of students coming from all the programs of the campus in terms of relationship with other people are not significantly different.

Table 3. *Significant difference between the Level of Stress of the Students from the Different Programs of the Campus*

<i>Programs (BSBM MM, BSBM HRM, BSHM, BSE, BSINDT/BSCPE, BSIT/BSCS) and Stress</i>	<i>F-Value</i>	<i>P-Value</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
School- related Factors	3.679	0.012	Significantly different
Relationship	0.519	0.762	Not significantly different
Body, mind and feelings	8.063	0.000	Significantly different

Quality of Study Habits of the Students

Table 4 shows that generally, the students mostly replied that they sometimes do the habits which are explicated in the survey, thus, they have good study habits in terms of their motivation, organizing and planning, their working with others, utilizing resources and feedback, and their note-taking and reading.

Table 4. *Quality of Study Habits of the Students in CvSU Carmona Campus*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Average Score</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Motivation	49.06	Good
Organizing and planning	66.00	Good
Working with others, utilizing resources and feedback	45.08	Good
Note-taking and reading	66.89	Good

Motivation. Mainly, students on all programs had an average score of 49.06 which means they have a good quality of study habits in terms of motivation (Table 4). This shows that students sometimes get down to work but can be distracted. Also, they might not always be certain why they have to work. They probably could benefit from learning some techniques that help them get down to work more consistently and keep at it. It shows that students mostly are somehow motivated which is clearly displayed since most believe that they exert effort to find out why they need to do a particular task. Also, they are somehow willing to do the tasks (activities, requirements, etc.) they do not enjoy because they see it as important, and they see to it that they give themselves regular breaks from studying. With this, it shows that they have an acceptable or tolerable study habits in terms of being motivated to study.

Organizing and Planning. In terms of organizing and planning, the students of the campus mostly have good study habit with an average score of 66.00. This simply exposes that students are not as well-organized as they can be. Their time management may benefit from a closer analysis. Yet as seen the average score is near 70 which is interpreted as very good. This is noticeable since most of them review their work before submitting it, submit all their assignments on time, prioritize tasks that should be done first, make a review schedule for examinations, and make a list of their things to do. This shows that they may not be as well-organized as they can be but they can manage their time as to their school activities.

Students have different ways of handling their studies. They use different strategies to surpass things. Students in a study by Tus (2020) in Bocaue, Bulacan showed to be doing their assignments and will never stop until it is completed, keep their work for every subject together and carefully arranged them and makes it a point that they try to make up for missed lessons even without reminders from their teachers. Thus, they have effective study procedures, and are competent enough in doing any academic assignments, and have effective how-to-study skills.

Working with Others, Utilizing Resources and Feedbacks. The table shows a 45.080 average score which exhibits that the students have a good study habit in terms of working with others, utilizing resources and feedbacks. It means that students probably collect resources, but they need to ask themselves how to use them more effectively. Most of these students listen out for key ideas when someone is talking, try to anticipate what they will say next whenever they are listening to someone, and they ask questions and generally take part in group discussions. As observed also most of them never cut from newspapers and magazines which may be of help to them in terms of information and do not mostly see TV programs which may be useful to them. This is surely because of the occurrence of information is already available over the internet. Generally, they do try to look for people who can help them or resources they can use but sometimes use the information ineffectively which still makes an acceptable study habit.

Note-taking and Reading. The average score of students of CvSU Carmona in terms of note-taking and reading is 66.89 which is interpreted as good. This mean that students' reading and note taking skills are adequate, but could still be improved. It shows that this result was mainly because most of the students listen for key ideas when listening to a speaker/teacher, they underline or highlight key ideas so they stand out, their notes indicate the main ideas rather than merely repeat what has been said, they look for summaries at the end of chapters, and even check the contents page for relevance before reading a book. This clearly shows they have good study habit in terms of note taking and reading but it can still be made better and enhanced.

Furthermore, the significant difference on the quality of study habits of the different programs of the campus were measured. It can be

seen that the quality of study habits in terms of working with others, utilizing resources, and feedback and the note-taking and reading habits of the students from all the programs of the campus, when compared to one another, are significantly different from one another (Table 15). But the quality of study habits of the students in terms of motivation and organizing and planning are not significantly different from one another.

Table 5. *Significant difference between the Quality of Study Habits of the Students from the Different Programs of the Campus*

<i>Programs (BSBM MM, BSBM HRM, BSHM, BSE, BSINDT/BSCPE, BSIT/BSCS) and Factors</i>	<i>F-Value</i>	<i>P-Value</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Motivation	15.568	0.019	Not significantly different
Organizing and Planning	17.431	0.065	Not significantly different
Working with others, utilizing resources, and Feedback	32.347	0.000	Significantly different
Note-taking and Reading	42.198	0.000	Significantly different

As revealed in studies, different personal behaviors exist in connection to studying habits (Arora, 2016) which in connection to Kamoru and Gbolagade (2017) stated that study habits is a combination of study method and skill, vary from person to person, and are the key to success. In addition, the qualities, talents, and preferences of a learner are referred to as their learning style information that humans receive and process (Hsieh, Jang, Hwang & Chen, 2011).

Level of Academic Performance of Students of CvSU Carmona Campus

Table 6 demonstrates that most students have a very good academic performance with a grand general point average (GPA) of 1.78. Altogether, most of the students are doing great in their studies. It can also be observed that the programs with the highest GPA are the programs of Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSE) with 1.63 GPA, Bachelor of Science in Hospitality Management (BSHM) with 1.64 and Bachelor of Science in Business Management major in Marketing Management (BSBM MM) with a GPA of 1.74.

Table 6. *Level of academic performance of the students in Cavite State University - Carmona*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>GPA</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
BSBM MM	1.74	Very Good
BSBM HRM	1.75	Very Good
BSHM	1.64	Very Good
BSIT	1.92	Very Good
BSCS	1.95	Very Good
BSIndT	1.92	Very Good
BSCpE	1.72	Very Good
BSE	1.63	Very Good
Grand GPA	1.78	Very Good

Even though some studies, including those by Hasan and Bao (2020), concluded that the pandemic has negatively affected students as higher education institutions transitioned to online learning, the results of this study determined that the students of CvSU - Carmona Campus demonstrated a very good academic performance with a grand grade point average of 1.78. According to Aguilera-Hermida (2020), the pandemic has also brought positive effects on students, including increased family interaction, increased parental supervision, and the ability to engage in extracurricular activities and hobbies that are less likely when they must attend school. These positive effects may have an impact on how well students perform academically.

Relationship between the Level of Stress of the Participants and their Academic Performance

Table 7 below shows the relationship between the level of stress of the students and their level of academic performance using the Pearson Correlation Coefficient. With a p-value of 0.013, 0.000, and 0.00 respectively, it generally shows that the level of stress in terms of school-related factors, relationship, and body, mind and feelings are all significantly related to their academic performance. It means that whatever their stress level in terms of the said factors has something to do with the academic performance of the students.

Table 7. *Relationship between the level of stress of the participants and the level of academic performance of CvSU Carmona Students*

	<i>r</i>	<i>P-Value</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
School-related factors and academic performance	0.081	0.013	Significantly related
Relationship and academic performance	0.130	0.000	Significantly related
Body and mind feelings and academic performance	0.104	0.000	Significantly related

School-related factors and academic performance. With a p-value of 0.13, school-related factors are found to be significantly related to the academic performance of the students. This differ from the results of the analyses of Akgun and Ciarrochi (2010) when that time it uncovered that academic stress was negatively associated with the academic performance. This was mainly because of learned resourcefulness of the students. Since these times are within the pandemic period where students have limited resources because of

certain restrictions, there was a significant relationship found between school related activities and the performance of the students in their studies.

Relationship and academic performance. With a p-value of 0.13, school-related factors are found to be significantly related to the academic performance of the students. As ReachOut Australia (2022) stated, relationships are vital at any age. More than anybody else, young people need healthy relationships with their friends, families, and partners since these relationships can impact their physical health, promote a feeling of self-worth and belonging, and teach them social and problem-solving skills. Relationship problems can affect academic, professional, and career responsibilities and lead to stress and discontent. Another study also revealed that students rely more heavily on different people for academic support and personal issues. The students had positive relationships with their classmates, family, friends, and partners, influencing and supporting their efforts to pursue degrees.

Body and mind feelings and academic performance. With a p-value of 0.13, school-related factors are found to be significantly related to the academic performance of the students. Mohamad, Baidi, Asshidin, Mohamad, and Subhi (2017) obtained the same findings. They emphasized that the students' academic-related stress has an adverse effect on their mental and physical health and contributes to various academic issues. Specifically, according to Pascoe, Hetrick, and Parker (2019), stress-related disruption of sleep is a significant factor in poor student learning and wellbeing. The growth of health issues, such as chronic non-communicable diseases, can also be attributed to academic stress because of declines in physical activity and increases in poor lifestyle choices.

Relationship between the Quality of Study Habits of the participants and their Academic Performance

As displayed in Table 8, the relationship between the quality of study habits of students in terms of motivation and academic performance, organizing and planning and academic performance, working with others, utilizing resources and feedback and academic performance, and note-taking and reading and academic performance all resulted to a p-value of 0.000 which means they are all significantly related to one another. Simply, it reveals that the quality of study habits of students impacts the academic performance. Whatever change in the quality of study habits affects the academic performance and vice versa.

Table 8. *Relationship between the Quality of Study Habits of the participants and their Academic Performance*

Indicators	Chi-Square Value	P-Value	Interpretation
Motivation and academic performance	38.108	0.000	Significantly related
Organizing and planning and academic performance	48.234	0.000	Significantly related
Working with others, utilizing resources and feedback and academic performance	48.407	0.000	Significantly related
Note-taking and reading and academic performance	39.750	0.000	Significantly related

Motivation and academic performance. Table 8 shows a significant relationship between these variables as the result of the chi-square test led to a p-value of 0.000. This means that the motivation of the student does have something to do with their academic performance. This is in connection to the study using the Learning and Study Strategies Inventory (LASSI) to predict student success Hendrickson (1997) discovered that the best indicators of student success were motivation and attitude. In general, the study habit of the students under motivation received an overall remark of good which indicates that the students can be able to achieve their academic goal.

Organizing and planning and academic performance. With a chi-square value of 48.234 and a p-value of 0.000. This means that how well students organize and plan their activities in life does have something to do with their academic performance. Study of Sore, Onyango, and Nyagol (2017) showed that there is a very strong positive correlation between schools which use strategic planning and the students' academic performance. It was confirmed when a comparison was done in the mean scores of grades before and after the introduction of strategic plans in schools by the ministry.

Working with others, utilizing resources and feedback, and academic performance. As displayed in the table above, a chi-square value of 48.407 and a p-value of 0.000 shows that there is a significant relationship between the academic performance of the students of the campus and their study habits in terms of their working with others, utilizing resources and receiving feedbacks. This means that how well students organize and plan their activities in life does have something to do with their academic performance. This was in accordance with Nam and Zellner (2011) cited that those groups of students known as 'positive interdependence' groups had significantly higher achievement than those with no group structures at all. This reveals that it is better to work in groups with others getting comments and suggestions from others lead to a better academic performance.

Note-taking and reading, and academic performance. Table 8 shows a p-value of 0.000 as the result of the chi-square test of the said variables stating that there is a significant relationship between students' note-taking and reading activities and their academic performance. This means that whenever students take down notes and receive feedback in their studies, this affects their college academic performance. Literatures even confirm that notetaking strategies of students and even faculty members, regardless of sex, have had high positive effect on the students' learning (Haghighverdi et al., 2010).

Conclusions

Findings of the study revealed that, generally, the level of stress of the students in terms of school-related factors is high while in terms

of relationship and body, mind and feelings factors revealed to be low. This presented an alarming result showing that students are emotionally and physically drained with the demands of their school. Moreover, there is significant differences between level of stress of the students from the different programs of the campus in terms of school- related factors and body, mind and feelings, when compared to one another. It is very appealing to discover that that even with some high stress levels, specially in school-related factors, students still displayed good study habits in terms of motivation, organizing and planning, working with other people, utilizing resources and feedback, and their note-taking and reading skills. From these four factors, only working with others, utilizing resources, and feedback, and note-taking and reading were found significantly different form one another. All these still led to very good level of academic performance.

It is important to note that level of stress of students in terms of school-related factors, relationship, and body and mind feelings are all found to be significantly-related to academic performance of students. In the same way, it was revealed that student study habits in terms of motivation, organizing and planning, their working with others, their utilizing resources and feedback, and in terms of their note-taking and reading were also all found to be significantly related to their academic performance. Given the findings and conclusions of the study, the following implications and recommendations were constructed:

Stress relieving or stress-removing activities are suggested to be done to lessen, if not removed, the stress felt by students in universities which still utilize remote learning. Approach and delivery may be done differently per program especially with factors focusing on school-related activities and enhancing the body, mind and feelings.

Continuous conduct of department and or program orientation on students focusing on their career path and the essence of being a graduate under their chosen program to lessen the fear on it.

Continuous establishment or strengthening of partnerships and/or linkages for possible employment/internship and enhanced job fairs can be employed so to lessen the fear of not having a job after graduation.

Conduct of Health and Wellness Week both for students and faculty members, providing recreational activities, continuous podcast, creation of HELP (Holistic Engagement to Love and Protect) BOT, creation and development of health and wellness infomercial and the development of student organization or group focused only to protect and promote students' mental health, may support lessening the stress level of students and focus more on the relationship with others.

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